

Performance of an underwater glider with varying wing configurations

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Abstract. Underwater gliders are typically buoyancy-driven where the mechanical power required for motion through the fluid medium is provided by gravity in the form of net buoyancy. In this regard, a variable buoyancy engine mechanism is used for the thrust generation of the underwater glider for maintaining the required trajectory. In this study, the control surfaces are designed as simple rectangular wings placed symmetrically about the glider axis along the length, and they generate the hydrodynamic lift during glider operation. The performance of the glider for different pitching angles is investigated using numerical investigations. The influence of the fins on the flow characteristics and hydrodynamic performance is studied for varying fin configurations. It is observed that the fin design and positioning play important roles in governing the motion characteristics of the glider. Tapered wings provide more stability with respect to pitching than rectangular wings. Also, the addition of winglets impacts the lift and drag significantly, resulting in the increase of lift-to-drag ratio by around 10.9%. The results are important in the context of optimal fin configuration for motion control of underwater gliders.

Keywords: *Underwater glider, CFD, Wing configuration*

1 Introduction

Oceans cover over three-quarters of the Earth's surface area and are a critical source of sustenance, medicine and commerce. Ocean exploration requires Autonomous Underwater Vehicles, submarines, Remotely Operated Vehicles, surface ships and/or Autonomous Underwater Gliders (AUGs). Of all these vehicles the design of AUGs is exciting and challenging. AUGs are winged vehicles without active propulsion devices and are driven by buoyancy, similar to the air glider. They can be used in coastal defence and monitoring as they move very slowly offering a maximum speed of 1 – 2m/s without having any significant signature to detect their presence. The first underwater glider design was published by Stommel in 1989 [1]. In recent times, the design of AUGs is becoming increasingly complex because of the demands of high endurance, operation flexibility, deep and restricted water navigation, high payload, energy efficiency, and special mission requirements being placed by naval and oceanographic administrations, etc. To achieve motion in vertical plane, AUGs use the difference between gravity and buoyant forces in the form of net buoyancy (positive or negative). Similarly, to achieve horizontal motion the lift generated by wings can be manipulated to act perpendicular to the vehicle's trajectory. Because of this restriction, the horizontal translation occurs only when the flight path is inclined at a glide angle deviating from the horizontal plane in the direction of the vertical net force of gravity (upward for a positive net buoyancy and downward for negative net buoyancy). The inclined glide angle to the flight path ensures the generation of hydrodynamic forces namely, lift and drag to balance the net buoyancy and allows the AUG to achieve steady-state flight. The inclined flight path that produces this force balance also gives rise to a net vertical motion.

A few interesting observations about these AUGs are that they share some common characteristics, like torpedo shape and small size. These characteristics are required to reduce drag. However, torpedo-shaped bodies are highly incapable of hovering at a spot as they are unstable in pitch and roll, significantly affecting the glider's performance while operating very close to the bottom in harsh or rugged terrain. The instability in pitch can also be caused by a large separation between the Center of Buoyancy (CoB) and the Center of Gravity (CoG) of the vehicle. These instabilities can be overcome by installing a robust hover control. One of the ways to ensure this control is by having a Variable Buoyancy Engine (VBE) onboard. VBE consumes energy onboard for its operations, but ensures the glider achieves hovering capability. In the absence of VBE on the AUG, the operation of a vehicle with a slight trim angle can increase the drag and produce some lift on the body, which is undesirable. From this, it is clear that balancing the hydrodynamic forces acting on the AUG plays a predominant role in its performance [2].

A comparison of rectangular and tapered wings for an underwater glider was presented in [3]. Experiments on various parameters of tapered fins in a blended wing body were carried out in [4], and it was concluded that the lift-to-drag ratio depends on the base chord length. Thus, in our investigation, we are varying chord lengths to

observe their impact on hydrodynamic performance. Another idea is to add a winglet to tapered wings for drag reduction and improved overall stability [5]. There are also more sophisticated designs of late, wherein some characteristic features are bio-inspired, like the sweep angle of wings analogous to a swift bird [6] or a controllable wing mechanism as seen in humpback whale fins [7].

The operation process of an underwater glider contains continuous gliding and sampling along a saw-tooth trajectory. The gliding speed can be controlled by adjusting the driving-buoyancy and the pitch angle of the glider [8]. The present study considers a basic glider design with a cylindrical middle body and a hemispherical nose. A numerical study based on the hydrodynamic performance has been carried out to identify the influence of the wing location and design. Three wing positions are investigated along with the influence of tapering, and later a winglet has been added. Section 2 discusses the different shape configurations considered in the study, Section 3 discusses the CFD methodology and numerical schemes used in the study, followed by validation using the Myring body, which is a popular reference for underwater glider hull design [9]. Section 4 contains details on the results and discussions, followed by conclusions.

2 Design

In this study, a cylindrical middle body is considered to get the best structure and shape, as spherical hulls offer the best structural integrity [10]. The fins attached use NACA0012 as the airfoil, as it gives better lift than a flat plate [11]. Symmetrical foils have the same lift characteristics at both positive and negative angles of attack, which is ideal for the saw-tooth trajectory of the underwater glider. The main dimensions of the underwater glider model are presented in Table 1. The CAD model of the glider is shown in Figure 1.

2.1 Main Hull

Figure 1. Underwater glider model: Top, front, side, and isometric views. (All dimensions are in mm)

Table 1. Main Particulars of Underwater Glider

Length (mm)	660
Diameter (mm)	120

Wing Half Span (mm)	370
Chord (mm)	40
Design Speed (m/s)	0.5

2.2 Wing Position

Three positions along the length of the body have been considered, as shown in Figure 2, to analyse the optimal position of fins on the body. All simulations have been carried out with at a pitching angle of 15° of the body. The simulations are carried out at a flow velocity of 0.5 m/s and 1 m/s. The optimal position of the wing is decided based on the pitching moment values measured about the centre of gravity of the body.

Figure 2. Wings placed at three positions (a) at $L/4$, (b) at $L/2$ and (c) at $3L/4$. (All dimensions are in mm)

2.3 Hydrodynamic Derivatives Calculation

First, the resistance of the body for straight ahead motion (zero drift angle and zero angle of attack) is calculated for different flow velocities. Velocity derivatives are calculated by performing steady translational simulations for angle of attack α (-15° to $+15^\circ$) in the z-plane and drift angle β (-15° to $+15^\circ$) in the y-plane. Forces X (Surge), Y (Sway), and Z (Heave) and moments K (Roll), M (Pitch), N (Yaw) are calculated in the flow (earth-fixed) coordinate frame and then transformed to the body-fixed frame. A cubic equation is fitted to the plots (shown in Section 4.2) to get the slope or hydrodynamic derivative. All simulations are carried out at flow velocity 0.5 m/s.

2.4 Wing Design Modifications

The optimal wing position has been fixed based on the CFD results of the simulations in Section 2.2, after which the effect of tapered wings on the hydrodynamic performance of the glider has been analysed. For this, three wing designs have been considered, for which the base and tip chord lengths are varied, keeping the span area and span length of each wing constant. This idea is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Variation of chord lengths with area and span as constant. (All dimensions are in mm)

Three ratios of tip chord (C_t) to base chord (C_b), 1 (rectangular wings), 0.8, and 0.4 have been chosen as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Wing configurations with (a) $C_l/C_b = 1$, (b) $C_l/C_b = 0.8$ and (c) $C_l/C_b = 0.4$. (All dimensions are in mm)

For CFD simulation, flow velocity is kept as 0.5 m/s and the pitching angle of each body is varied from -15° to $+15^\circ$, with an increment of 5° , giving us a total of 3×7 test cases.

2.5 Winglet Addition

A winglet has been attached to the wing configuration with $C_l/C_b = 0.4$ (Figure 5). A single upper blended winglet has been used, which is the most common type in the aviation industry today. The winglet design with the most optimal drag reduction has been suggested in [5]. Figure 6 illustrates the dimensions of that winglet.

Figure 5. Underwater glider with winglet model: Top, front, side, and isometric views.

Figure 6. Winglet specifications. (All dimensions are in mm)

The body is kept at an angle of attack (α in the vertical plane, pitch direction) of 15° for this simulation at flow velocity = 0.5 m/s.

3 Methodology

3.1 Solution Settings

The numerical study was done using the Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes equation, which considered a single-phase steady viscous fluid. The Reynolds number for the solution is 3.29×10^5 , thus, SST k- ω turbulence model has been used in the commercial CFD software Ansys Fluent, which uses a finite volume approach. The inlet boundary condition is a velocity inlet, and the outlet is a pressure outlet. The circumference area of the domain cylinder is treated as a free slip wall, and the glider body is treated like a no-slip wall.

A cylindrical computational domain extending to 3L upstream and 5L downstream of the glider body is used, as shown in Figure 7 [12]. The radius of the domain is 2.5L. Around 8 million cells are used in the mesh, involving a combination of hexagonal and tetrahedral elements. Inflation layer has been added around the wall of the body to capture wall effects on flow characteristics closely.

A solver based on the finite volume method has been used to solve the integral equations of mass and momentum conservation. A second-order discretization scheme is used for pressure solving, and SIMPLE (Semi-Implicit Method for Pressure-Velocity Coupling) is used for pressure-velocity coupling. A second-order upwind scheme is used for the turbulence kinetic energy and the turbulence dissipation rate [13].

Figure 7. Domain and Mesh Details.

3.2 Validation Study

The Myring hull form is used to validate the CFD model. This is done by comparing the drag results of the geometry from CFD to the experimental data in the paper for various velocities. The specifications of the geometry are the same as in [13]. The computational domain and solution methodology is similar to the one described above. The comparison is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Drag values of Myring Hull

Flow Velocity	Drag (N) (CFD)	Drag (N) (Reference)	Percentage Error
1.5 m/s	4.948	5.2	6.7%
2 m/s	8.328	7.8	4.8%

4 Results and Discussions

4.1 Influence of wing position on Lift/Drag ratio

The results obtained from the simulations stated in Section 2.2 are presented in Table 3. The pitching angle of the body is 15° in all simulations. The pitching moment about centre of gravity is measured and analysed.

Table 3. Pitching moment variation with fin location

Flow Velocity	0.5 m/s	1 m/s
Location (mm)	Pitching moment (N-m)	

25% from fwd (165)	0.595	2.420
Mid (330)	0.170	0.436
25% from aft (495)	-0.394	-1.60

The stability with respect to pitching angle is maximum when the wings are placed at the middle of the body. All further wing design modifications have been done at this optimal position itself.

Figures 8 and 9 show the velocity and pressure contours for wings placed at the various locations. Pressure difference at the wings is seen, which produces the lift required.

Figure 8. Velocity contours for wing located at (a) L/4, (b) L/2 and (c) 3L/4.

Figure 9. Pressure contours for wing located at (a) L/4, (b) L/2 and (c) 3L/4.

4.2 Hydrodynamic Coefficients

The linear and non-linear derivatives due to the velocities- u (x-direction), v (y-direction) and w (z-direction) are calculated and shown in Table 4. These are important as they can be fitted into the Fossen's maneuvering model of six-degree of freedom motion equations, which combines rigid body motion with hydrodynamics [14].

Figures 10(a) and 10(b) show estimation of X_{uu} and X_u , and Z_{www} , Z_{ww} and Z_w respectively by curve fitting. All other derivatives have been calculated in a similar manner.

Table 4. Linear and Non-Linear Velocity derivatives

X Force (Surge) Derivatives					
X_{uu}	-1.87	X_{vvv}	-0.2785	X_{www}	1.0268
X_u	-0.21	X_{vv}	-9.205	X_{ww}	-0.322
		X_v	0.005	X_w	-0.0358

Y Force (Sway) Derivatives		Z Force (Heave) Derivatives	
Y_{vvv}	30.662	Z_{www}	1663.1
Y_{vv}	0.0261	Z_{ww}	0.0659
Y_v	-7.178	Z_w	-67.91
N Moment (Yaw) Derivatives		M Moment (Pitch) Derivatives	
N_{vvv}	-0.63	M_{www}	-57.21
N_{vv}	2×10^{14}	M_{ww}	0.0064
N_v	-0.902	M_w	2.2811

Figure 10. X Force vs (a) u velocity and (b) w velocity.

Surge (X) force is dominant when flow velocity is varied keeping both α and β as 0° . As a result, we get a value for hydrodynamic derivative of X with respect to u. Surge (X) and heave (Z) force, and pitch (N) moment is dominant when α is varied, resulting in hydrodynamic derivatives with respect to w. Sway (Y) force and yaw (M) moment is dominant when β is varied, resulting in hydrodynamic derivatives with respect to v.

4.3 Effect of tapered wings

In the following graphs (Figures 11, 12 and 15), tip chord has been expressed as a fraction of base chord in the legend.

(b)

(c)

Figure 11. Forces and moment: (a) X force or Drag (b) Z force or Lift and (c) Pitching moment vs Angle of Attack.

Figure 12. Lift-to-drag ratio vs Angle of Attack for various wing configurations.

The X force or drag reduces at higher angles of attack as the wing shape tapers more. The Z force or lift reduces at higher angles of attack as taper angle increases. Maximum lift-to-drag ratio decreases slightly as we increase the taper angle.

Figure 13. Velocity contours for (a) Rectangular wing and (b) Tapered wing ($C_t/C_b = 0.4$).

Figure 14. Pressure contours for (a) Rectangular wing and (b) Tapered wing ($C_t/C_b = 0.4$).

The pressure variation along non-dimensional chord is analyzed and plotted in Figure 15 to justify the behavior of the above plots. The pitching moment for rectangular and tapered wings are compared in Table 5, wherein the body has an angle of attack 15° , and the $C_t/C_b = 0.4$.

Table 5. Pitching moment variation with fin shape

Flow Velocity	0.5 m/s	1 m/s
Design	Pitching moment (N-m)	
Rectangular Wing	0.170	0.436
Tapered Wing	0.122	0.299

Figure 15. Coefficient of pressure (C_p) VS x/C .

The rectangular wing has a higher magnitude of pressure difference along the chord. This justifies the higher lift generation observed in case of the rectangular wing. On the other hand, tapered wings have a better pitching moment stability due to a better force distribution when compared with the rectangular wing.

4.4 Influence of Winglet

The effect of winglet has been investigated, wherein the winglet is attached to the tapered wing keeping $C_t/C_b = 0.4$. The simulation is carried out as described in Section 2.4 and the results are shown in Table 6. The lift and drag have increased on addition of the winglet, and the increase in lift is greater than the drag increment. As an outcome, the lift/drag ratio has increased by 10.9%.

Table 6. Effect of winglet on Lift and Drag

Design	Lift (N)	Drag (N)	Lift/Drag
With Winglet	4.91	1.75	2.80
Without Winglet	4.10	1.62	2.53

A comprehensive study may be done by extending this study to a rotating arm test and moving mesh to get all velocity and acceleration derivatives. That will allow a visualization of the trajectory, and conclusions on the hydrodynamic performance can be drawn.

5 Conclusion and Future Work

Through this study, different wing configurations have been studied for a simple glider design using CFD calculations. The positioning of the wing along the glider impacts the flow, and hence the resulting hydrodynamic coefficients governing the motions and pitching moment which is critical for a glider performance. The taper ratio has a finite effect on the flow hydrodynamics and lift performance of the glider. Between the different designs tested, the tapered wing configuration with a winglet has the best lift-to-drag ratio and lower pitching moment as compared to other cases. It is envisaged that dynamic simulations will be performed in future to obtain the hydrodynamic derivatives involving both horizontal and vertical plane motions for optimal path control of the glider.

As a follow-up of the numerical study, a small-scale physical prototype of the glider has been developed, which uses a water injection based variable buoyancy engine. The different parts of the glider are shown in Figure 16. The engine works in 3 phases: (a) Injection phase, wherein water is taken in to increase internal mass causing downward vertical motion, (b) Expulsion phase, wherein upward vertical motion is generated due to reducing internal mass, and (c) Pause phase wherein glider stabilizes at water surface and there is no change of mass. This cycle is controlled by regulating the buoyancy engine to obtain specific vertical motion parameters.

Figure 16. Physical model and engine components of the glider.

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